

Review

Seeing the Light after 25 Years of Retinal Gene Therapy

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The retina has been at the forefront of translational gene therapy. Proof-of-concept that gene therapy could restore vision in a large animal led to the initiation of the first successful clinical trials and, in turn, to the recent approval of the first gene therapy product for an ocular disease. As dozens of clinical trials of retinal gene therapy have begun, new challenges are identified, which include delivery of large genes, counteracting gain-of-function mutations, and safe and effective gene transfer to diseased retinas. Advancements in vector design, improvements of delivery routes, and selection of optimal timing for intervention will contribute to extend the initial success of retinal gene therapy to an increasing number of inherited blinding conditions.

The Retina at the Forefront of Translational Gene Therapy

In December 2017, the FDA approved the first gene therapy product for an inherited disease in the USA [1]. This made history in the gene therapy field. The newly approved gene therapy product is being used to treat patients affected by **Leber congenital amaurosis type 2 (LCA2; see Glossary)**, an inherited retinal degeneration (IRD) caused by mutations in *RPE65* that results in severely impaired vision at birth and then slowly progressive degeneration of retinal photoreceptors [2]. The drug voretigene neparovec (Luxturna), is an adeno-associated virus (AAV)-based vector that includes a correct copy of *RPE65*.

Given the advantages that the eye offers as a target organ for gene therapy, it has been at the forefront of translational research of gene therapy. The eye is enclosed and relatively immune privileged given the presence of physical barriers, including the blood–retinal barrier, and the local inhibition of immune responses by the unique intraocular microenvironment [3]. These features prevent vectors from disseminating systemically and the immune system from reacting against the vector components and/or transgene product. Retinal cells do not proliferate after birth; thus, a single injection of a vector can lead to an indefinitely long-lasting expression of the transgene, even in the absence of transgene integration. This characteristic, along with the small size of the eye, makes it a very attractive target tissue because only small amounts of recombinant vectors are required to treat patients, thus overcoming the challenge of large-scale viral vector production. Many small and large animal models of IRDs are available that are instrumental to provide proof-of-concept of the efficacy of the therapies. In addition, *in vivo* imaging techniques, such as **optical coherence tomography, adaptive optics scanning laser ophthalmoscopy**, and fundus autofluorescence [4–6], have been developed that allow defining the efficacy of gene therapy over a long period through non-invasive and repeated monitoring of retinal status. Procedures for human subretinal surgery were already available before research on gene therapy for eye diseases started being developed and have been easily adapted to transfer genetic material into specific ocular compartments.

Highlights

The first FDA-approved gene therapy product for an inherited disease is an adeno-associated virus (AAV)-based vector for a form of blindness.

Clinical development of gene therapy for dozens of rare and common retinal diseases is ongoing, although improvements will be required to broaden the success of retinal gene therapy to a growing number of conditions.

Transduction of the retina from the vitreous and delivery of genes larger than 5 kb are long-standing goals of the field, for which promising results have been recently obtained in animal models.

The recent evolution of designer nucleases, including CRISPR/Cas9, allows to edit toxic gain-of-function mutations even in terminally differentiated neurons.

Therapeutic approaches which are independent of the underlying mutations are being developed that are based on delivery of either neurotrophic factors to slow down retinal degeneration or optogenetic molecules to sensitize neurons to light.

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The Road from the First Proof-of-Concept Study to Dozens of Clinical Trials in Humans

Initial attempts to identify vectors for retinal gene delivery date back to the mid-1990s. The first vector tested for its ability to transduce both retinal pigment epithelium (RPE) and photoreceptors, which are the main target cells for gene therapy of IRDs, was an Adenovirus (Ad)-based vector [7,8]. Upon its **subretinal injection**, the RPE was efficiently transduced, while photoreceptors appeared refractory to transduction with Ad and required higher vector doses. However, further studies demonstrated that gene transfer to photoreceptors was enhanced in the newborn retina and in animal models of IRDs at the pre-degenerate state [8], possibly due to reduced physical barriers. Soon after followed the first demonstration of successful gene therapy using Ad vectors in the rd1 mouse model of a recessive inherited retinal degeneration caused by mutations in the beta subunit of the cGMP phosphodiesterase [9]. Meanwhile, the evaluation of the retinal transduction profiles of alternative viral vectors began. Subretinal administration of HIV type 1-based lentiviral (LV) vectors resulted, similarly to Ad, in efficient transduction of RPE and photoreceptor transduction that was higher in newborn than in adult rats [10]. More promising results in terms of photoreceptor transduction were obtained with AAV vectors [11,12], which demonstrated efficient transduction of both photoreceptors and RPE after subretinal injection. In the following years, the retinal transduction profiles of dozens of different Ad and AAV serotypes and LV pseudotypes were evaluated in search of the best candidate vector for retinal gene therapy [13]. Despite these efforts, none of the Ad- and LV-based vectors tested thus far have reached the levels of photoreceptor transduction achieved with AAV vectors [13,14]. One possible explanation could be that the large size of Ad and LV particles imposes steric constraints that hamper the viruses' diffusion through the physical barriers of the adult retina [15–17]. More recently, non-viral vectors have been considered for retinal gene delivery and found to be effective, at least in the short term, in some animal models of IRDs [18–22]. However, concerns regarding the duration of the effects of the treatment and the efficiency of transduction, especially in large animal models, have limited broad development of these non-viral vector-based strategies for retinal gene therapy.

The favorable retinal transduction properties of the first AAV vectors boosted further small- and large-animal studies, as well as attempts to isolate or engineer AAV variants with higher transduction levels, different tropisms, and the ability to transduce the retina through the less invasive **intravitreal injections**. While some of these needs have not been satisfied yet, AAV-mediated gene delivery has led to significant improvement of the retinal phenotype in dozens of IRD animal models [13,23]. These studies have established AAV as the vector of choice for retinal gene transfer. This was confirmed when subretinal delivery of an AAV2 vector encoding for *RPE65* was found to restore vision in the large dog model of LCA2 [24]. These outstanding results led to the initiation of three different clinical trials involving AAV2-based subretinal delivery of *RPE65* in LCA2 patients. Despite differences in vector and trial design, all trials showed that AAV-mediated gene therapy was safe and effective, with improvements in visual acuity, pupillary reflex, light sensitivity, and ability to navigate in dim light [25–27]. Importantly, a follow-on Phase I trial demonstrated that injection in the contralateral eye of three LCA2 patients who had been previously treated with the same vector was safe and effective [28]. Based on these encouraging results, Spark Therapeutics launched an advanced Phase III clinical trial in which bilateral subretinal administration of AAV2-RPE65 was accomplished in LCA2 patients as young as 4 years old [29]. This trial confirmed the safety and efficacy profile of the therapy and provided the necessary data to support the market authorization granted by FDA in December 2017.

These LCA2 trials have also shown some of the challenges in translating successful proof-of-concept studies to effective therapies in humans. In two (NTC00481546, NTC00643747) of the

Glossary

Adaptive optics scanning laser ophthalmoscopy: imaging technique based on the combination of confocal laser scanning microscopy for acquisition of retinal images and adaptive optics to remove optical aberrations to obtain sharper images.

Alstrom syndrome: disease inherited as autosomal recessive, which combines features including retinal dystrophy, obesity, and insulin resistance. It is caused by bi-allelic mutations in *ALMS1*, which encodes for a ciliary/centrosomal protein thought to play a key role in transport along the photoreceptor cilium.

Choroideremia: disease inherited as X-linked recessive, which leads to the degeneration of choroid, RPE, and photoreceptors. It is caused by mutations in *CHM/REP1* that encodes the Rab escort protein 1 (REP1).

Fovea: small central area of the primate retina with the highest density of cone photoreceptors. It is responsible for high-acuity and color vision.

Intravitreal injection: intraocular injection that delivers vectors in the vitreous and exposes the anterior retina to transduction. It is less invasive than subretinal injections.

Leber congenital amaurosis type 2 (LCA2): disease inherited as autosomal recessive, which results in severe hypovision early in life. It is caused by bi-allelic mutations in *RPE65*, which encodes for the isomerase that promotes visual chromophore recycling in the RPE.

Light-sensitive microbial opsins: membrane channels that upon light stimulation undergo conformational changes that result in alterations of the membrane potential of the retinal cells similar to those induced by the phototransduction cascade.

Optical coherence tomography: volumetric imaging of the retina through the use of a near-infrared light.

Stargardt disease: most common form of inherited macular degeneration in humans. Inherited as autosomal recessive, it is caused by bi-allelic mutations in *ABCA4*, which encodes for a photoreceptor-specific all-*trans*-retinal transporter, involved

three clinical trials, a decline in the levels of visual improvements was reported, suggesting that the treatment was unable to halt the underlying retinal degeneration [30,31]. This was in contrast to the studies in the dog model of LCA2 that showed stable, long-lasting efficacy [32,33]. Additionally, differently from what was observed in dogs, no improvement in the full-field electroretinogram was observed in any of the patients enrolled in the trials. Whether these results depend on the higher levels of RPE65 expression needed in the human retina than in the canine retina [31] or on the timing of treatment, which might have been too late to halt photoreceptors degeneration [33], remains to be determined. However, these trials served as an important lesson to underline that successful proof-of-concept studies in animal models do not necessarily perfectly translate to humans, and further optimization of therapy might be required at the clinical trial stage. Indeed, one of the groups involved in the first clinical trials has moved ahead with the development of a new version of the gene therapy product for LCA2, which involves the use of an AAV5 vector and an optimized *RPE65* expression cassette. This new vector was found to be, at least in mice, 300 times more potent than the vector used in the original trial [34]. A Phase I/II clinical trial that uses this improved vector is in progress (NCT02946879). Recently, the results of an additional LCA2 clinical trial (NCT01496040) have been published. This trial was launched to investigate the efficacy of *RPE65* delivered by AAV4, a serotype that in animal models was found to selectively transduce the RPE [35]. Another difference between this LCA2 clinical trial and the previous studies was a higher number of subretinal injections used to deliver the vector, in an attempt to increase treatment efficacy. Disappointingly, results of functional tests revealed variable modifications after treatment and less evident improvements in the treated eyes compared to results of the first trials, potentially because of the ~10 times lower dose of vector used in this trial.

Although gene therapy for LCA2 might still need further refinements, the positive results obtained so far have encouraged broader application of gene therapy for IRDs. The outcomes of the ongoing clinical trials targeting other retinal diseases (Table 1) will improve our understanding on the safety and efficacy of particular vectors, routes of administration, and doses. As an example, the results from the **choroideremia** (CHM) gene therapy trial (NCT01461213) showed a high degree of safety associated with subretinal injections targeting the **fovea** [36,37], a concern that had been raised in the previous LCA2 trials [38,39].

How Easily Will the Success of the LCA2 Trials Be Replicated for Other Diseases?

The reason for the relatively rapid clinical development of gene therapy for LCA2 is that it is a very good target for gene therapy at both molecular and clinical levels. Indeed, LCA2 is an autosomal recessive disease caused by mutations in a small gene that encodes an enzyme expressed in the RPE layer, which is efficiently transduced by AAV vectors. Additionally, the slowly degenerative nature of the disease provides a favorable ‘therapeutic window’ in which to intervene on retinal function by increasing RPE65 enzymatic activity in residual cells. Other IRDs that are purely degenerative, and/or caused by mutations that are either gain of function or located in large genes, pose greater challenges for gene therapy.

Delivery of Large Genes

Many transgenes are too large to be effectively packaged in AAV vectors, whose cargo capacity is limited to approximately 5 kb of DNA [40]. However, none of the alternative Ad, LV, or non-viral vectors tested thus far have convincingly matched the levels of photoreceptor transduction obtained with AAV [13,41]. Thus, considerable efforts have been made to identify strategies to expand AAV transfer capacity. We and others have shown that large transgenes can be split into two separate AAV vectors (dual AAV, Figure 1) that, upon co-infection of the same cell, reconstitute

in the recycling of the visual chromophore.

Subretinal injection: intraocular injection that delivers vectors into a virtual space between the RPE and the photoreceptors, inducing a regional and reversible retinal detachment called ‘bleb’.

Usher 1B syndrome: most severe form of combined retinitis pigmentosa and deafness. Inherited as autosomal recessive, it is caused by bi-allelic mutations in *MYO7A*, which encodes for an unconventional myosin expressed in both photoreceptors and RPE.

Table 1. Gene Therapy Clinical Trials for Retinal Diseases Using Recombinant Viruses

Target disease	Vector	Sponsor	Phase	NTC no.
Achromatopsia	AAV8-hCARp.hCNGB3	MeiraGTx UK II Ltd	I/II	03001310
	AAV2tYF-CNGA3	Applied Genetic Technologies Corp	I/II	02935517
	AAV2tYF-CNGB3	Applied Genetic Technologies Corp	I/II	02599922
	AAV-CNGB3	MeiraGTx UK II Ltd	I/II	03278873
Choroideremia	AAV2-hCHM	Spark Therapeutics	I/II	02341807
	AAV2-REP1	University of Oxford	II	02407678
	AAV2-REP1	University of Miami	II, completed	02553135
	AAV2-REP1	University of Oxford	I/II, completed	01461213
	AAV2-REP1	University of Alberta	I/II, completed	02077361
	AAV2-REP1	STZ eyetrial	II	02671539
Leber congenital amaurosis 2	AAV2-hRPE65v2	Spark Therapeutics	I/II (follow on)	01208389
	AAV5-OPTIRPE65	MeiraGTx UK II Ltd	I, II	02946879
	AAV2-hRPE65v2-301	Spark Therapeutics	III	00999609
	AAV2-hRPE65v2-101	Spark Therapeutics	I/II	00516477
	AAV5-OPTIRPE65	MeiraGTx UK II Ltd	I/II	02781480
	AAV2.hRPE65p.hRPE65	University College, London	I/II, completed	00643747
	AAV2-hRPE65	Applied Genetic Technologies Corp	I/II, completed	00749957
	AAV2-hRPE65	University of Pennsylvania	I	00481546
	AAV2-hRPE65	Hadassah Medical Organization	I	00821340
	AAV4-hRPE65	Nantes University Hospital	I/II, completed	01496040
Leber hereditary optic neuropathy	scAAV2-P1ND4v2	University of Miami	I	02161380
	AAV2-ND4	GenSight Biologics	III	02652780
	AAV2-ND4	GenSight Biologics	III	02652767
	AAV2-ND4	Huazhong Univ of Science and Technology	II/III	03153293
	AAV2-ND4	Huazhong Univ of Science and Technology	I/II, completed	01267422
	AAV2-ND4	GenSight Biologics	I/II	02064569
	AAV2-ND4	GenSight Biologics	III	03293524
Neovascular/age-related macular degeneration	AAV.sFLT1	Lions Eye Institute, Perth, Western Australia	I/II, completed	01494805
	AAV2-sFLT01	Genzyme (Sanofi)	I	01024998
	AAV8-AntiVEGF	Regenxbio Inc.	I	03066258
	AAV-CD59	Hemera Biosciences	I	03144999
	LV (Retinostat)	Oxford BioMedica	I, completed	01301443
	LV (Retinostat)	Oxford BioMedica	I	01678872
Retinitis pigmentosa	AAV-ChR2	Allergan	I/II	02556736
	AAV2-hMERTK	Fowzan Alkuraya	I	01482195
	AAV2.7m8-ChrimsonR-tdTomato	GenSight Biologics	I/II	03326336
	AAV8-hRLBP1	Novartis Pharmaceuticals	I/II	03374657
	AAV5-hPDE6B	Horama S.A.	I/II	03328130
Stargardt disease	LV (SAR422459)	Sanofi	I/II	01367444
	LV (SAR422459)	Sanofi	I/II	01736592

Table 1. (continued)

Target disease	Vector	Sponsor	Phase	NTC no.
Usher syndrome type 1B	LV (Ushstat)	Sanofi	I/II	01505062
	LV (Ushstat)	Sanofi	I/II	02065011
X-linked retinitis pigmentosa	AAV-RPGR	NightstaRx Limited	I/II	03116113
	AAV2-RPGR	MeiraGTx UK II Ltd	I/II	03252847
	AAV2tYF-RPGR	Applied Genetic Technologies Corp	I/II	03316560
X-linked retinoschisis	AAV-RS1	National Eye Institute (NEI)	I/II	02317887
	AAV2tYF-hRS1	Applied Genetic Technologies Corp	I/II	02416622

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Figure 1. Dual AAV Vectors for Large Gene Delivery to the Retina. Two separate adeno-associated virus (AAV) vectors are used to deliver both the 5' (orange) and the 3' (light blue) halves of a large gene to photoreceptors. The full-length gene expression cassette is reconstituted in the nucleus of photoreceptors transduced by both vectors via intermolecular recombination between the two AAV vector genomes.

the expression of a full-length gene via intermolecular recombination between the two AAV vector genomes [42–44]. Although the resulting protein expression mediated by dual AAV is lower than that achieved with a single AAV vector [44,45], it was sufficient to improve the retinal phenotype of mouse models of both **Stargardt disease** and **Usher IB syndrome** (USHIB) [44]. Indeed, a Phase I/II clinical trial testing the safety and efficacy of dual AAV in the retina of USHIB patients is being planned.¹ More recently, AAV transfer capacity has been expanded up to 14 kb, albeit at the expense of efficiency, by adding a third vector to the dual system (triple AAV) [46]. The levels of transduction achieved in the retina of a mouse model of **Alstrom syndrome** with triple AAV led to

only modest and transient improvement of the phenotype [46]. However, the significantly higher transduction efficiency of triple AAV vectors in the pig than in the mouse retina bodes well for further optimization of this platform. This result also confirms that co-infection by multiple AAV vectors is favored in the subretinal space of larger animals, as observed for dual AAV [45]. In addition, strategies that can improve single or multiple AAV transduction, such as the combined delivery of kinase inhibitors with AAV [47], may help to bring multiple AAV-based strategies to the required efficacy to move from bench to bedside.

An alternative for large gene delivery to the retina might be LV vectors, which have larger genome capacities than AAV vectors. Although the ability of LV to transduce photoreceptors is still questioned, two Phase I/II clinical trials involving LV-mediated delivery of the large *ABCA4* and *MYO7A* gene to the retina of Stargardt and USH1B patients (NCT01367444 and NCT01505062), respectively, have been launched. The results from these trials will provide important data on the suitability of LV for gene therapy of IRDs caused by mutations in genes expressed in photoreceptors.

Identification of AAV with Improved Transduction Properties

An important and still debated issue in retinal gene therapy is whether subretinal injections, which result in transient detachment of RPE from the underlying photoreceptors, should be avoided in a diseased retina rendered fragile by the undergoing degenerative process. This issue can be particularly relevant when the subretinal injection involves the fovea, the thinnest and most fragile region of the retina, which is crucial for central vision. While the results from the CHM trial argue against this [36], evaluation of alternative routes of injection is under investigation. Although the recently developed sub-inner limiting membrane injection results in inner retina transduction using canonical AAV vectors [48], the intravitreal delivery represents the least invasive, and thus potentially safer, procedure to transduce the retina (Figure 2). Additionally, this delivery route offers the advantage of a widespread distribution of the vector through the vitreous to the retina. Unfortunately, when injected intravitreally, most viral vectors, including the majority of AAV serotypes, do not transduce photoreceptors and RPE [49], presumably because of the presence of physical barriers between the vitreous and the outer retina, such as the inner limiting membrane.

Strategies to solve this issue include rational design, which modifies residues of the AAV capsids that are known to be crucial for the transduction process, or directed evolution in which libraries of randomly generated mutant capsids are exposed to selective pressure [50]. Both strategies have led to the identification of novel AAV variants such as quadruple and pentuple tyrosine mutants or AAV2-7m8, which were shown to transduce the outer retina from the vitreous in small animal models [51–53] (Figure 2). However, their intravitreal injection in larger animals, such as dogs and non-human primates (NHPs), fails to reproduce the same levels of outer retina transduction observed in mice [53–55], presumably because of the presence of thicker barriers in larger animals than in mice, which prevent AAV diffusion, or to the substantial dilution of the vector in the vitreous of larger eyes that requires use of high doses of vectors to reach the outer retina. Indeed, higher levels of foveal and extrafoveal photoreceptor transduction were observed when AAV2-7m8 was administered intravitreally to NHP either at high doses, which resulted in toxicity when combined with a ubiquitous promoter, or at low doses combined with strong cell-type-specific promoters [53,55,56].

Treatment of Autosomal Dominant Diseases

Dominant forms of retinitis pigmentosa (RP) are identified in >30% of patients with a recognizable pattern of inheritance [57]. Mutations in the rhodopsin gene (*RHO*), collectively, are the

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Figure 2. Photoreceptor Transduction via Intravitreal Injection. Differently from natural adeno-associated viruses (AAVs), AAV vectors with improved ability to penetrate the retina, generated through either rational design or directed evolution, can transduce photoreceptors and the retinal pigment epithelium (RPE) upon delivery from the vitreous.

most common cause of autosomal dominant RP [58]. Several mutations are common and cause a toxic gain-of-function effect, which requires silencing of the mutant allele rather than gene augmentation to obtain therapeutic efficacy. Much interest has thus been directed toward development of approaches to silence the *RHO* gene that have been tested in animal models carrying the common P23H and P347S mutations found in RP patients. Both *RHO* allele-specific and -independent approaches, the latter directed at complete suppression of *RHO*, have been explored [58] and showed challenges. Indeed, allele-specific ribozymes and short hairpin RNA have been used with variable degrees of efficiency [59–61]. Vice versa, allele-independent silencing has demonstrated rhodopsin reduction of up to 90% [62]. However, this strategy poses the challenge to provide, in parallel to the suppression, a copy of *RHO* that is resistant to the silencing agent to restore proper levels of *RHO* expression. This can be demanding given that *RHO* is the most abundant protein in photoreceptors and that replacement at levels below 50% of the endogenous might convert an often mild dominant disease into a more severe recessive condition. Proof-of-concept studies have shown that this silencing and replacement strategy can improve the retinal phenotype of rodent models of RP [62–64]. More

recently, Botta and colleagues developed a new allele-independent approach for *RHO* silencing that uses a 'dead' artificial transcription factor that by solely binding to *RHO* promoter (present in only two copies per cell) suppresses *RHO* expression, while avoiding additional genome-wide transcriptional perturbations [65].

The new generation of genome editing tools, such as Zn-finger nucleases, TALE nucleases, and CRISPR/Cas9 [66], which allow modifications of a gene at its locus (Figure 3), appears particularly suitable for treatment of autosomal dominant RP. These systems allow precise induction of double-strand breaks at specific genomic loci, which are repaired by either non-homologous end joining, potentially knocking out specific dominant mutant alleles, or by homologous recombination that allows precise correction of the mutation using a donor DNA template. Among these systems, CRISPR/Cas9 is proving to be particularly versatile and precise at inducing gene correction. Thus, its investigation for therapeutic applications in a variety of diseases, including IRDs, is increasing significantly. However, one of the major concerns in the use of CRISPR/Cas9 is the possibility of inducing unintended off-target mutations in the genome; this issue is particularly important in post-mitotic tissues, such as the photoreceptors, where AAV-mediated Cas9 expression will persist long term after a single subretinal injection, thereby increasing the potential for off-target effects. Still, given its enclosed structure, the eye, might be an ideal organ in which to investigate the safety of this cutting-edge platform. The initial reports on the use of CRISPR/Cas9 in the retina of rodent models of

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Figure 3. Genome Editing for Treatment of Autosomal Dominant Diseases. Dominant forms of inherited retinal diseases, such as those caused by gain-of-function mutations in the rhodopsin gene, require silencing of the mutant allele to result in therapeutic efficacy. Genome editing mediated by Zn-finger or TALE nucleases or CRISPR/Cas9 is being explored for this purpose. Genome editing tools are designed to induce precise double-strand breaks at specific genomic loci (i.e., the mutant allele), which can be then repaired by either non-homologous end joining or homologous recombination, resulting in either knockout or precise correction of the mutation.

dominant RP showed a significant, yet partial, improvement of the phenotype [67–71]. Thus, despite these encouraging results, the still relatively low efficiency of genome editing poses questions on its therapeutic potential [72]. Optimization of photoreceptor transduction or on-target correction efficiency is required before Cas9-mediated genome editing can be applied to most IRDs. Notably, in addition to the obvious dominant conditions, genome editing may be applicable to recessive diseases due to mutations in genes that are either too large to be packaged into AAV vectors, or toxic if overexpressed from heterologous promoters [73,74].

Improving Vision Independently of the Causative Gene

More than 260 genes are associated with retinal diseases,ⁱⁱ posing a particular challenge when developing approaches specific for each of these genes. Thus, identification of mutation-independent therapeutic strategies has been a longstanding goal of the field. Among them are strategies in which neurotrophic molecules, such as ciliary neurotrophic factor (CNTF) [75], glial cell line-derived neurotrophic factor [76,77], basic fibroblast growth factor [78], and rod-derived cone viability factor [79] or antiapoptotic proteins, such as X-linked inhibitor of apoptosis [80], are delivered via AAV vectors to the retina. These have shown the potential to prolong photoreceptors cell survival, although in some cases (CNTF) at the expense of photoreceptor function [81]. However, none of these strategies have been tested in humans yet, with the exception of CNTF, which has shown limited efficacy [82].

An alternative mutation-independent strategy is represented by optogenetics, which is also particularly suited for advanced cases of IRDs in which no viable photoreceptors are present.

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Figure 4. Optogenetic to Restore Vision in Advanced Cases of Retinal Degeneration. When no viable photoreceptors are left by the degenerating disease, adeno-associated virus (AAV)-mediated delivery of light-sensitive opsins to bipolar or retinal ganglion cells, which are spared by the degeneration, can be used to activate retinal circuits downstream of the degenerated photoreceptors. Indeed, upon light stimulation, opsins undergo conformational changes that result in activation of either bipolar or ganglion cells.

In these cases, delivery of either **light-sensitive microbial opsins**, such as channelrhodopsin or halorhodopsin [83,84], or opsins native to the human eye, such as rhodopsin [85] and melanopsin [86], to bipolar or retinal ganglion cells can be explored to activate the retinal circuit downstream of potentially dysfunctional or absent photoreceptors (Figure 4). Limitations to the application of these tools come from either their low light sensitivity that requires abnormally high light intensities to be effectively excited, as for channelrhodopsin or halorhodopsin, or from their slow kinetics, as in the case of melanopsin. This field is therefore constantly focused on the identification of channels with improved characteristics. Another key point for development of effective optogenetic tools is restoring complex visual responses. Indeed, while effective in restoring retinal responses, optogenetics therapies targeting the retinal ganglion cells bypass the important step of stimulus propagation to the inner retinal circuitry. Targeting the outermost surviving retinal layers would instead allow greater levels of signal processing. In this direction, transduction of both primate foveal cones via intravitreal delivery [56] and of bipolar and horizontal cells through subretinal injection have been recently successfully achieved [87]. Whether remodeling of the inner retina, which occurs in advanced stages of retinal degeneration [88,89], can impact on the long-term efficacy of these approaches needs to be investigated.

Concluding Remarks

Over the past 25 years, there has been significant progress in developing retinal gene therapy. Once AAV was established as the vector of choice for retinal gene therapy, most of the efforts of the field have been directed toward overcoming some of the challenges this platform presents. A planned clinical trial for USH1B¹ will ultimately define whether the levels of expression achieved with dual AAV vectors are therapeutically relevant in humans (see Outstanding Questions), thus overcoming the limitations imposed by AAV cargo capacity. Yet, dual AAV capacity is insufficient for delivery of genes larger than 9 kb. Unless a way to increase levels of transduction from multiple AAV vectors is found, treatment of IRDs caused by mutations in genes larger than 9 kb will be probably more effectively pursued through genome editing than gene replacement. Identification of vectors capable of transducing photoreceptors from the vitreous also seems an achievable goal (see Box 1). Rational design and directed evolution have proved to be useful techniques to develop new AAV vectors with improved transduction properties in mice. However, thus far, none of these vectors have confirmed widespread transduction of the outer retina in large animal models, highlighting the inability of small animal models to fully recapitulate the physical barriers present in larger eyes. Although challenging, directed evolution of novel AAV performed directly in larger species seems the next step necessary to identify a vector that can ultimately efficiently transduce photoreceptors upon intravitreal delivery in a primate retina.

Disease-associated challenges, as gain-of-function mutations or advanced degeneration, have proven to be more difficult to overcome than those inherent to the delivery platform. Innovative tools, such as programmable nucleases for genome editing or optogenetics, may succeed in this

Box 1. Clinician's Corner

Inherited retinal degenerations are a major cause of blindness worldwide.

The first gene therapy product for an inherited form of blindness was approved at the end of 2017.

Vectors are being developed that target the outer retina following an intravitreal administration.

Vector platforms are being developed to deliver large genes.

Gene delivery of optogenetic molecules converts retinal cells into light-sensing neurons in photoreceptor-less retinas.

Outstanding Questions

Are the levels of transgene expression achieved with dual AAV vectors sufficient for therapeutic efficacy in humans?

Can non-viral vectors be used to achieve efficient transduction in large eyes?

Can directed evolution in non-human primates lead to the identification of AAV serotypes that efficiently transduce the retina from the vitreous?

Are neurotrophic factors effective at halting retinal degeneration in humans?

Which is the most effective combination of optogenetic tools and target cells to restore proper retinal circuits?

Which are the repair mechanisms necessary to achieve the highest levels of genome editing in the retina?

Is prolonged expression of Cas9 safe in non-proliferating cells as photoreceptors?

How predictive of efficacy in humans is testing in animal models in terms of both transduction levels and time frame for effective intervention?

Is subretinal injection safe in advanced cases of retinal degeneration?

Which is the optimal therapeutic window for intervention in each inherited retinal disease?

Can gene therapy halt progression of the disease in an already degenerating retina?

Which are the most appropriate endpoints to evaluate therapeutic efficacy in clinical trials?

but still require optimization before they can be brought to patients. In the retina, where homologous recombination occurs at low rates, precise genome editing will need to exploit alternative mechanisms such as non-homologous end joining used for homology-independent targeted integration [90]. In the case of advanced retinal degeneration, therapies based on stem cells, whether genetically modified or not, are a valuable alternative to *in vivo* gene delivery [91–93]. Also in this case, the eye offers unique safety advantages. So far, RPE cells (reviewed in [91–93]) have been more easily and reproducibly generated *in vitro* than photoreceptors. Patients with macular dystrophies have been transplanted with RPE derived from either human embryonic stem cells [94] or human induced pluripotent stem cells [95], so far with limited efficacy.

Additional challenges that the field of retinal gene therapy is facing include the need for robust outcome measures to be used in clinical trials in addition to canonical visual acuity, as well as the definition of diseases natural history which is particularly relevant for degenerative conditions like IRDs to select the optimal window of opportunity for effective intervention.

In conclusion, after 25 years of retinal gene therapy, treatment has become achievable for an increasing number of retinal degenerations.

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Resources

ⁱhttps://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/212674_it.html

ⁱⁱ<https://sph.uth.edu/retnet/>

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